

EVALUATION METHOD OF JOINING STRENGTH OF CF RTP MANUFACTURED BY HYBRID INJECTION MOLDING PROCESS

Fumiya Matsumoto¹ and Kazuaki Nishiyabu²

¹ Department of Management of Industry and Technology, Graduate School of Engineering,
Osaka University, 2-1 Yamadaoka, Suita, Osaka, Japan

Email: matsumoto-f19@mit.eng.osaka-u.ac.jp

² Department of Mechanical Engineering,
Kindai University, 3-4-1 Kowakae, Higashiosaka, Osaka, Japan,

Email: nishiyabu@mech.kindai.ac.jp

Web page: <https://www.kindai.ac.jp>

Keywords: CF RTP, CF/PA66, Hybrid injection molding, Single lap shear strength

ABSTRACT

Hybrid injection molding is a method which is combined injection molding and hot press molding. This method is possible to produce molding articles of high rigidity, high strength and complication shape. In hybrid injection molding, a thermoplastic CFRP laminated material is heated and press molded into a desired shape by clamping, followed by injection molding of a molten polymer and joining with the laminate. Therefore, it is important to improve the reliability of the joining strength of a molded product formed by hybrid injection molding. In general, the joining strength is evaluated by a tensile shear test. However, in the tensile shear test of CFRP, when the rigidity of the test piece is insufficient with respect to the tensile load, deformation occurs, and the bending moment is considered to influence the stress state of the joint. In addition, when the joining strength exceeds the tensile strength of the injection molded part, the injection molded part is broken. Therefore, it is not applicable to evaluate quantitatively the joining strength. In this study, in order to improve the reliability of the joining strength of the CFRP parts manufactured by hybrid injection molding, the deformation behaviour of the test piece in the tensile shear test is investigated and an appropriate evaluation method using the auxiliary jig is proposed. The test piece was prepared by hybrid injection molding using a CF/PA66 laminate and a short CF/PA66 pellet using a near-infrared heater as a heating device. The deformation behaviour and stress distribution of the specimen in the tensile shear test is investigated by three-dimensional strain distribution measurement. As a result, in the modified method, it was found that the tensile failure at the short CF/PA66 is suppressed and the shear failure can be occurred at the joint.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic (CF RTP) is manufactured by various methods such as injection molding, hot press molding and automated tape placement. The reinforcement form of the fibers used is varied by the manufacturing method, so that the mechanical properties and the degree of freedom of the shape of the article are changed remarkably. Hybrid injection molding is an advanced manufacturing method which is combined injection molding and hot press molding. In the injection molding method, short fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer is melted and plasticized with extruder and injected inside the metallic mold cavity with high pressure. Thus, it is very excellent in mass production of molded parts with complicated shapes, but the mechanical properties are insufficient. In hot press molding, on the other hand, the continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic polymer laminated material such as woven fabrics and unidirectional fibers is well used, and it is heated with various heating sources before pressing by a metallic die. Thus, it can be applied to a structure member with high rigidity and high strength. Therefore, by combining these two methods, it is possible to manufacture the high-performances molded products with high rigidity, high strength and complicated shape, and also high productivity and manufacturing cost are also effective [1, 2]. In a hybrid injection molding, a thermoplastic CFRP laminated material is heated to the melting temperature of the matrix

polymer and pressed by closing a mold, and it is followed by injection molding of a molten polymer. In this process, these materials are melt-bonded. Therefore, it is important to enhance the reliability in joining strength of a molded product manufactured by hybrid injection molding. Therefore, the evaluation of the joint properties for the molded products which is hybrid injection molding is done. The tensile strength of the joint between the laminates and the injection molding polymer is investigated by a tensile test using a T-type specimen [3]. In addition, the shear strength is evaluated generally by a tensile shear test using a single lap test specimen. However, in the single lap shear test specimen, out-of-plane deformation occurs under the tensile loading and the bending moment is considered to influence the stress state of the joint. In addition, it is impossible to evaluate quantitatively the joining strength because the tensile fracture occurs mostly when the joining strength exceeds the tensile strength of the injection molded part [4]. Therefore, in order to evaluate the shear strength, a tensile shear test method using a jig has been proposed [5]. However, when using a jig, there is no report that investigated the behavior of the specimen under test because the joint is covered with the jig. In this study, a modified evaluation method was proposed by using a jig to obtain the tensile shear strength of the joining specimen prepared by hybrid injection molding. The deformation behavior and stress distribution of the specimen in the tensile shear test is investigated by three-dimensional strain distribution measurement.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material properties

The material used for test specimen was woven CF/PA66 laminate (LANXESS, TEPEX®, $V_f=45\text{vol.}\%$) with a thickness of $t=0.75\text{mm}$ and short CF/PA66 polymer (Toray, 3101T-30V, fiber weight ratio 30wt.%) as shown in Table 1. It is shown from the result of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis that the glass-transition temperature is $T_g=50^\circ\text{C}$ and the melting temperature is $T_m=260^\circ\text{C}$. It is also shown from the result of thermogravimetric analysis (TG) that the thermal decomposition temperature is $T_d=350^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 1: Material used for test specimen

	Inserted laminate	Polymer pellets
ID	Woven CF/PA66	Short CF/PA66 pellets
Fiber content, V_f	45 [vol.%]	30 [wt.%]
Reinforcing configuration	2x2-twill weave	Short fiber
Stacking sequence	[0/90] ₃	-
Thickness, t	0.75 [mm]	-
Surface image		

2.2 Hot Press-Injection Hybrid Molding Process

Fig. 1 shows the schematic drawing of manufacturing process by hot press-injection hybrid molding. This process is proceeded in 4 steps as follow: (a) Inserting a thermoplastic CFRP laminate into mold, (b) Heating the thermoplastic CFRP laminate to the melting temperature of the matrix polymer by near-infrared heater, (c) Injection molding of non-reinforced polymer or short fiber reinforced polymer after closing the mold and (d) Demolding of specimen after cooling to the glass transition temperature of the matrix polymer. Table 2 shows molding parameters for hot press-injection hybrid molding. Insert injection molding was performed using an injection molding machine (FANUC CORPORATION, ROBOSHOT a-150i). The short CF/PA66 polymer pellets were predried at 80°C for 6 hours using a hot air drier (MATSUI MFG. CO., Ltd., HD2). The injection mold was set at 80°C using a mold temperature controller (MATSUI MFG. CO., Ltd., MCH-25). Fig. 2 shows the shape of the molded product and the cut-out position of the test piece. Three test pieces with a width of

13 mm were cut out at a position of 5 mm from the end of the molded product. This is because burrs of molded products may affect the test results. A diamond cutter (Ishii Super Tool Co., Ltd., DX Wide Cera Lotus) was used to cut out the test pieces.

Figure 1: Manufacturing process of hot press-injection hybrid molding.

Table 2: Molding parameters of hot press-injection hybrid molding.

Preheating	Heater power [%]	75
	Heating time [s]	40
	Distance between heater and laminate [mm]	65
Injection	Clomping force [kN]	750
	Injection speed [mm/s]	85
	Maximum Injection pressure [MPa]	80
	Holding pressure [MPa]	15
	Temperature of mold [°C]	80
	Temperature of cylinder [°C]	275

Figure 2: Shape of product and cutting position.

2.3 Tensile shear strength test

The single lap shear strength (SLSS) test was carried out to measurement tensile strain of the surface on the SLSS specimen with a universal testing machine (Shimadzu Co., Ltd., AG-50kN XDplus) and non-contact three-dimensional strain measuring device (GOM mbH, ARAMIS®) at room temperature. The crosshead speed was 0.5mm/min. Fig. 3 shows the shapes of the SLSS specimens of the conventional method and the modified method. Before the SLSS test, aluminum tabs were bonded to specimens with epoxy adhesive (Huntsman Japan, Araldite® Rapid). Also, in the modified method, an L-shaped jig and a support jig were attached to the SLSS specimen in order to suppress the tensile failure in the short CF/PA66. The effect of L-shaped jig is adding a compressive load instead of the tensile load to the short fiber CF/PA66 and the effect of the support jig is suppressing the bending deformation by reinforcing the rigidity from the outside. Therefore, the SLSS strength of the joint can be evaluated because the tensile failure does not occur in modified method.

Figure 3: Schematic of the SLSS specimen.

3 RESOULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 4 shows the results of the SLSS test. In the conventional method, when the tensile load reaches 1250N and 1650N, the short CF/PA66 had a tensile failure. On the other hand, in the modified method, shear failure occurred at the joint when the tensile load reached 2683N and 3268N. Fig. 5 shows the tensile strain distribution of SLSS specimen. In the conventional method, the concentration of the tensile strain occurred in the front of the short CF/PA66 at 1250N. In the tensile strain distribution at the side, bending deformation was occurred because tensile strain and compressive strain are simultaneously seen in the short CF/PA66 at 1650N. On the other hand, in the modified method, the concentration of the tensile strain was not occurred in the front. The strain distribution on the side is dominated by compressive strain at the top of the joint due to the compressive load by the L-shaped jig. Fig. 6 shows the relationship between maximum tensile strain in the front of the specimen and load. In the case of the conventional method, the maximum tensile strain $\varepsilon_{y_{max}}$ linearly increases with the increase of the load P , and when the load P is 1250N and a tensile failure occurs in the short CF/PA66, the maximum tensile strain $\varepsilon_{y_{max}}$ exceeds 1.2%. On the other hand, in the case of the modified method, the tensile strain ε_y gradually increases, and when the load P is 2683N and shear failure occurred at the joint, the maximum tensile strain $\varepsilon_{y_{max}}$ is about 1.0%. Especially, when the load P is 1250N, the maximum tensile strain $\varepsilon_{y_{max}}$ of modified method was 70% smaller than that of the conventional method. Therefore, it was shown that the increase of tensile strain ε_y is suppressed by using the modified method, and it becomes possible to measure the tensile shear strength τ in the range which could not be measured by the conventional method. However, even when using the modified method, the maximum tensile strain $\varepsilon_{y_{max}}$ continues to increase gradually, so if the tensile shear

strength τ is further increased, there is a risk that tensile failure may occur in the short CF/PA66, and improvement is necessary.

Figure 4: Results of the SLSS test.

Figure 5: Tensile strain distribution of SLSS specimen.

Figure 6: Relationship between maximum tensile strain in the front of the specimen and tensile load.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we proposed a evaluation method for the joining strength of hybrid injection molded products using woven CF/PA66 laminates and short CF/PA66, and verified its effectiveness. As a result, in the modified method, it was found that the tensile failure at the short CF/PA66 is suppressed and the shear failure can be occurred at the joint.

REFERENCES

- [1] Mario A. Valverde, Robert Kupfer, Luiz F. Kawashita, Maik Gude, Stephen. R. Hallett, "Effect of processing parameters on quality and strength in thermoplastic composite injection overmoulded components" Proceedings of 18th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM-18), 2018.
- [2] Jan P. Beuscher, Raphael Schnurr, Anke Müller, Markus Kühn and Klaus Dröder, "Process development for manufacturing hybrid components using an in-mould infrared heating device" 18th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM-18) (2018).
- [3] Tanaka, K., R. Noguchi, and T. Katayama. "Effects of preheating temperature on the interfacial tensile strength for glass fiber reinforced polypropylene composites made by press and injection hybrid molding." WIT Transactions on The Built Environment 166 (2016): 287-296.
- [4] Aurrekoetxea, J., et al. "Failure of multimaterial fusion bonding interface generated during over-injection molding/thermoforming hybrid process." Journal of applied polymer science 102.1 (2006): 261-265.
- [5] Pisanu, L., L. C. Santiago, J. D. V. Barbosa, V. E. Beal, and M. L. F. Nascimento. "Strength shear test for adhesive joints between dissimilar materials obtained by multicomponent injection." International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives 86 (2018): 22-28.